

Cyclone Risk Perception Among Institutionalised Elderly Women in Puducherry, India

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study explores cyclone risk perception among elderly residents in institutional care settings in Puducherry.

Method: An exploratory qualitative design was used, involving two focus group discussions with nine elderly women in an old-age home. Data were analysed thematically to identify patterns in cyclone risk perception and preparedness.

Result: Analysis revealed seven themes: knowledge and risk communication on cyclones; lived experiences and perceived impacts; emotional, psychological, and physical responses; coping mechanisms, faith, and trust in systems; institutional care and collective safety; the role of family and community; and expectations, acceptance, and perceived needs.

Discussion: Risk perception among institutionalised elderly women is shaped by lived experiences, frailty, faith-based coping, and dependence on institutional care. Gaps in communication, infrastructure, and preparedness highlight the need for inclusive, age-transformative disaster policies that strengthen institutional readiness, integrate active ageing principles, and encourage elderly participation.

INTRODUCTION

Climate-induced disasters are among the growing threats in today's world. The global disaster management landscape is increasingly shaped by the convergence of rapid population ageing and climate change-driven escalation in the frequency and intensity of hydro-meteorological hazards, such as cyclones, which often overwhelm local adaptive capacities (HelpAge International, 2023; Harris & Mihnovits, 2015). The number of disasters reported globally has risen from about 250 in the 1990s to about 400 over the past 10 years (Gutman & Yon, 2014), underscoring the urgent need to address this issue. Older adults have proven to be exceptionally vulnerable to climate-related disasters. During the 2011 Japanese tsunami, individuals aged 65 and over accounted for 56% of fatalities despite representing only 23% of the population, while 75% of those who died during Hurricane Katrina in 2005 were aged 60 or over (Harris & Mihnovits, 2015). This indicates that older adults are particularly vulnerable to these changes. The number of elderly people worldwide is expected to reach 2 billion by 2050, indicating that if an inclusive system is not developed, they will be disproportionately affected by future disasters (HelpAge International, 2015; Age International, 2018).

It is concerning that 27 of 36 states and union territories in India are vulnerable to natural disasters. About 8% of India's landmass is at particular risk from cyclones due to the country's extensive and vulnerable coastline (Muhammad et al., 2024). India's senior population is expected to grow rapidly, reaching approximately 138 million by 2021 (Government of India, 2021). Disaster preparedness frequently concentrates on institutional capacity or physical infrastructure, leaving the psychological and social aspects of elderly risk perception largely unaddressed, despite improvements in national disaster management frameworks (Hota & Rishi, 2017). Being a member of a vulnerable group and residing in a disaster-prone area creates a double marginalisation that necessitates additional attention from the system. Older adults' opinions are almost completely absent from disaster risk reduction (DRR) planning because existing research frequently views them as passive recipients of assistance rather than active participants (HelpAge International, 2023).

This study focuses on the Puducherry district in the Union Territory of Puducherry, a cyclone-prone coastal area in south-eastern India characterised by high geographical vulnerability and direct exposure to the Bay of Bengal (Government of India, 2021; Saravanan et al., 2018). The northern Tamil Nadu and Puducherry coast is recognised as highly prone to depressions and severe cyclonic storms, which frequently result in massive inundation and infrastructure damage (Saravanan et al., 2018). As per

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Puducherry Union Territory data, People aged 55 and older are considered elderly (Jothi et al., 2016), and this classification calls for specific policy attention and age-sensitive preparedness strategies for this cohort (HelpAge International, 2007; Government of India, 2021). Institutionalised residents in this area face significant obstacles despite this official recognition, such as restricted mobility, caregiver dependency, and limited access to timely, comprehensible warning information (Malak et al., 2025).

The institutionalised elderly women, who experience double marginalisation, require specific attention and can be understood through the lens of intersectionality theory, as introduced by Kimberlé Crenshaw in 1989. The intersectional lens provides a better understanding of gendered vulnerability, where age intersects with other axes of vulnerability. For these women, vulnerability is not merely a product of age, but an intersection of gendered roles, physical decline, and institutionalisation (Kwan & Tam, 2021; Matlakala et al., 2024). Physically, age-related changes such as muscle atrophy and sensory loss increase older adults' risk of injury and limit their ability to respond during rapid evacuations, while psychologically, they are vulnerable to displacement-related trauma and post-traumatic stress disorder, often intensified by the loss of routine and privacy in overcrowded shelters (Bayraktar & Yilmaz, 2018; Malak et al., 2025). Socially, older women often bear lifelong caregiving responsibilities and gendered expectations while facing systemic neglect and invisibility in humanitarian data, resulting in standardised aid that overlooks their specific medical and nutritional needs, underscoring the importance of examining institutionalised elderly women's perspectives to inform inclusive, evidence-based disaster interventions (Age International, 2018; Hamidazada et al., 2019). The significance of this study not only centres on the voices of the institutionalised elderly, a group often sidelined in mainstream disaster research, but also on identifying gaps in institutional preparedness from the residents' own perspectives. The primary aim of the study is to explore the cyclone risk perception of elderly women residing in institutional care settings. The objectives of this study are to investigate the knowledge and perceptions of cyclones and related risk factors among institutionalised elderly women. Then, to explore the experiences of the past cyclone in Puducherry among the respondents. The study also examines the preparedness and safety measures implemented by institutions in the event of a cyclone. Finally, to explore the coping strategies respondents employ and their needs related to disasters, particularly cyclonic events.

METHODOLOGY

This research used a qualitative approach and utilised an exploratory study design, conducting Focused Group Discussions (FGDs) to explore the collective narratives of elderly residents in an old-age home in Puducherry who have been affected by cyclones, using purposive sampling. For that, nine respondents were selected, all of whom were elderly women. The first FGD included five respondents, and the second FGD included four respondents. The nine respondents, included of elderly women who are aged 55 years or above who are residing in an institutional setting, along with those who have experienced cyclonic events. The respondents who are diagnosed with any mental illnesses and who are not eligible to provide the data are excluded from the study. Data were transcribed verbatim and analysed using thematic analysis through systematic coding and theme development. The study involved minimal risk, and ethical principles, including informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and sensitivity to participants' emotional well-being, were strictly upheld throughout the research process.

RESULT

Table 1 presents the thematic analysis of the focused group discussions, which revealed seven major themes reflecting elderly women's perceptions, experiences, and responses to cyclones within both community and institutional contexts.

Table 1: Thematic analysis of the data

Theme	Sub-Themes	Initial Codes
Knowledge, Awareness, and Risk Communication on Cyclones	Knowledge, understanding, and meaning-making of cyclones	A cyclone is understood as strong wind, rain, and cold. Simple physical understanding of cyclones; Limited technical knowledge of cyclone origin and movement
	Exposure and personal background	Understanding cyclones through past experiences; Long-term exposure to multiple hazards; Experience of tsunami alongside cyclones

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	Sources of information, alerts and early warnings	Television as primary source of cyclone information; Radio/FM radio warnings; Mobile phone alerts; Informal community communication
	Awareness of government support	No awareness of NDMA role; Lack of awareness about official helplines; Government alerts recalled vaguely via media
Lived Experiences and Perceived Impacts of Cyclones	Sensory memories and lived experiences	Loud wind and cyclone sounds; Visual memory of fallen trees; Remembering damaged houses and deaths
	Perceived impact on people and livelihoods	Damage to houses and belongings; Loss of livelihood and daily wages; Economic insecurity following cyclones
	Mobility and physical constraints	Water entering houses; Repeated flooding experiences; Cyclone-related displacement
Emotional, Psychological, and Physical Health Responses	Emotional responses to cyclones	Fear on hearing the word “cyclone”; Anticipatory fear before impact; Panic during flooding
	Physical, mental, and psychological well-being	Shivering, cold exposure, fever; Psychological distress during disasters; Anxiety triggered by disaster news
	Ageing and acceptance	Reduced fear due to repeated exposure; Acceptance of death due to old age; Emotional numbness over time
Coping Mechanisms, Faith, and Trust in Systems	Coping strategies	Staying indoors; Closing doors and windows; Yoga and exercise for stress relief

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	Religion and belief systems	Praying to God during cyclones; Leaving fate to God; Faith reducing fear and stress
	Trust and authority	Trust in God above institutions; Trust in institutional authority (“sir”); Acceptance of disasters as inevitable
Institutional Care, Collective Support, and Safety	Institutional supports and care	Evacuation to upper floors; Provision of food, water, clothes, and medicines; Institutional health monitoring
	Institutional experience during cyclone	Feeling safer in institutional settings; Staff-led disaster response; Institutional management during waterlogging
	Collective coping and solidarity	Elderly supporting each other; Strong residents helping weaker ones; Collective safety in shared spaces
Role of Family and Community in Disaster	Family and social context	Separation from family during institutionalisation; Concern for family safety despite separation
	Family relationships and communication	No communication with family during disasters; Institution facilitating family contact
	Community vs institution	Greater fear in hometown; Limited community support; Perceived greater safety in institution
Expectations, Acceptance, and Perceived Needs	Expectations and acceptance	Low expectations from government support; Passive acceptance of government actions
	Perceived needs and resignation	Acceptance of whatever support is provided; Desire for collective safety; No articulated future needs

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1. Knowledge, Awareness, and Risk Communication on Cyclones

Participants in institutionalised settings showed a basic, experience-driven understanding of cyclones, commonly describing them as characterised by strong winds, heavy rainfall, cold weather, and physical destruction. Knowledge about cyclones was largely shaped by past disaster experiences rather than formal disaster awareness. Risk communication was primarily mediated through mass media like television, radio, and newspapers, serving as the main sources of early warnings and information about cyclones. Informal community communication also played a role in disseminating alerts. However, awareness of official disaster management mechanisms for the elderly, such as government helplines or the role of national agencies and state agencies, remained limited, with participants remaining excluded from institutional planning. These perceptions are reflected in participants' narratives, as one participant explained:

“On FM radio at 6.45 am, we hear about a cyclone alert, and we pray for all.”

Another participant described their understanding of cyclone movement and government response:

“Cyclone originates from the Bay of Bengal and reaches Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Gujarat, so if given proper alert, we can reach safer places. The government will give food during the cyclone.”

Limited awareness of formal support systems was also evident, as one participant stated:

“Don't know about the helpline number, sir; only take care of these things.”

2. Lived Experiences and Perceived Impacts of Cyclones

Participants shared their experiences with cyclones, including memories of uprooted trees, damaged houses, broken roofs, waterlogging, and the loss of household belongings. Sensory memories, particularly the sound of strong winds and visual experiences of destruction, were frequently recalled. Cyclones were perceived to have severe impacts on the livelihoods of people, particularly for rural households and itinerant workers, resulting in economic instability and displacement. Several participants linked repeated exposure to disaster events to their eventual relocation into institutional care. Within institutions, experiences of cyclones were characterised by collective evacuation to safer spaces, such as upper floors, and peer groups supporting each other. These lived experiences were articulated through participants' narratives, as illustrated below.

One participant described the extent of housing damage and subsequent displacement:

“In Sankaranpettai, while we were at home, all the rooftops in the home went away; only walls were there then. With my husband, I shifted to Pondicherry for daily wage work.”

Another participant recalled the cumulative impact of major cyclones on personal security and well-being:

“During the Thane and Gaja cyclones, trees fell, and many houses were hit by the cyclone; it created fear about whether it would get us into a bad stage of life.”

Experiences within the institution were also noted, particularly related to flooding:

“Waterlogging happened in the institution.”

3. Emotional, Psychological, and Physical Health Response

Most elderly participants possess vivid recollections of past cyclones, fostering fear, anxiety, panic, and anticipatory distress, often intensified by prior disaster events like the tsunami that happened in 2004. One participant poignantly expressed the absence of community support, highlighting feelings of isolation. While some expressed resignation linked to advanced age and repeated exposure to hazards, these emotional responses significantly shape their risk perception. Physical health concerns included shivering, cold-related illnesses, fever, cough, and increased vulnerability among those with chronic conditions. Psychological stress emerged as a prominent outcome of disaster exposure, and the elderly with pre-existing physical conditions are suffering more. These vulnerabilities underscore the compounded risks faced by institutionalised elderly during and after such events. These emotional and physical vulnerabilities were reflected in participants' own words, as illustrated below.

One participant described the intense fear and bodily reaction triggered by cyclone sounds:

“While hearing the sound itself, it creates fear and body shivers.”

Another participant highlighted the heightened health risks faced by elderly individuals with chronic illnesses:

“There are heart patients; they will get frequent fevers.”

4. Coping Mechanisms, Faith, and Trust Systems

Faith and religious beliefs emerged as major coping mechanisms for participants. Many described prayer and surrender to god as primary strategies for managing fear and uncertainty during cyclones. Trust in God was frequently prioritised over trust in institutions and formal disaster management systems. At the same time, institutional authorities were regarded as secondary sources of trust, particularly during emergency situations, as they provide essential needs during such events even though the elderly remain excluded from disaster management planning and preparedness. This reliance on faith-based coping coexisted with practical strategies such as staying indoors and following institutional instructions during cyclone alerts. Active ageing manifests through voluntary actions, such as draining stagnant water and supporting peers, positioning participants as informal support networks even though it is not planned. Institutional leadership and staff play proactive roles in preparedness and response, though participants

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perceive less autonomy in these settings compared to community environments. Family involvement in recovery remains minimal, with surrounding communities and government departments contributing little or none, leading to lowered expectations; participants express readiness to accept whatever aid is provided by authorities or stakeholders. These coping strategies and trust systems are reflected in participants' narratives, as illustrated below.

One participant emphasised reliance on faith during crises:

“No one comes at that time; only we believe in God.”

Another participant highlighted collective support within the institution:

“If one or two persons are strong in our institution, they provide support to all others.”

The role of wellness practices in coping with stress was also noted:

“During stressful times, yoga helps us.”

5. Institutional Care, Collective Support, and Safety

Institutional care played a crucial role in shaping participants' sense of safety during cyclones. Participants highlighted the proactive role of institutional leadership and staff in ensuring their protection, including evacuation arrangements and provision of food, water, clothing, medicines, and regular health monitoring. Institutional mechanisms lack in inclusive planning, even though collective engagement is supported in the way that some elderly take a leading role in providing support during a cyclone. The institution was consistently described as a safer and more reliable environment than community settings during the cyclone. These perceptions are reflected in participants' accounts, as illustrated below.

One participant emphasised the protective role of institutional leadership:

“Our sir will take care of us during the rain; he won't allow us outside, and he gives all the essential things.”

Another participant highlighted the consistent provision of essential support within the institution:

“In the institution, they come, see us, and provide all essential items.”

6. Role of Family and Community in Disaster

Participants' narratives reflected complex and often fragile family relationships in the context of disasters. Many reported limited family support during cyclones, characterised by reduced communication and a greater reliance on institutions rather than family members. In community settings, support from neighbours and local authorities was recalled in some instances, particularly during evacuations and relief distribution. However, participants contrasted this with the sustained support in terms of basic needs and physical health support received in institutional settings. Feelings of emotional distance from family members coexisted with continued concern for their safety during disasters. These experiences are illustrated in participants' own words below. One participant expressed reluctance of house owners in allowing elderly persons in rental houses in fear of funeral rituals that may happen in their house, pointing down age discrimination driven by cultural superstitions. Community and government support near the institution was not reported by any participants in the institution.

One participant described the absence of familial communication during a crisis:

“I called my son; he didn't pick up.”

Another participant highlighted housing-related exclusion and social stigma faced in community settings:

“In the rental house, they don't allow us for fear of rituals when we die.”

7. Expectations, Acceptance, and Perceived Needs

Participants expressed low expectations regarding disaster-related support, particularly from government systems, and most of the respondents expressed no expectations or wishes as they are in the last stage of life. Many adopted an attitude of acceptance, indicating that they would receive and adjust to whatever assistance was provided. Rather than demanding specific needs, participants emphasised gratitude for existing institutional care and expressed wishes for others' safety. This sense of acceptance was often linked to age, life stage, and reliance on faith, reflecting a broader resignation toward future disaster risks that need to be addressed, promoting active ageing and making institutional settings an inclusive environment. These are reflected in participants' narratives, as illustrated below.

One participant expressed a diminished sense of hope regarding external support:

“We don't have that much hope.”

Another participant conveyed acceptance and a lack of articulated expectations:

“We have no wishes.”

Overall, the findings reveal that elderly women's cyclone risk perception is shaped by their lived experiences, emotional memories, faith-based coping mechanisms, and institutional support systems. While knowledge and awareness remain largely informal, institutional care emerges as a critical protective factor, compensating for the limited engagement of families and governments with

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the support like providing basic needs at critical time, providing yoga training but the institution still needs to make an arrangement for inclusive planning for disaster risk reduction involving the participants whom they are working for to make elderly population engaging promoting active ageing as most of the respondents fall into the art of acceptance with the basic needs provided by the institution. The results highlight the intersection of age, gender, place, and social support along with institutions in shaping disaster experiences among institutionalised elderly women.

DISCUSSION

The findings are synthesized through seven interconnected themes: Knowledge, Awareness, and Risk Communication on Cyclones, which examines how older adults make meaning of disaster warnings; Lived Experiences and Perceived Impacts of Cyclones, capturing memories and cyclone experiences that happened in institution; Emotional, Psychological, and Physical Health Responses, documenting the well-being of elderly population; Coping Mechanisms, Faith, and Trust in Systems, exploring support systems that exist for the elderly participants; Institutional Care, Collective Support, and Safety, highlighting basic support provided by the institution during and after cyclonic events, lack of inclusive planning, mobility constraints and care structures; Role of Family and Community in Disaster, examining the social context of isolation; and Expectations, age based discrimination, minimal support from the community and government, Acceptance, and Perceived Needs, which outlines the elderly residents' requirements for future disaster risk reduction, recovery and rehabilitation.

In answering the general aim of the study, it was found that risk perception among institutionalised older adults is a dynamic construct influenced by the intersection of physiological frailty, previous disaster experiences, lack of inclusive planning and a high degree of dependency on institutional caregivers. Hutton (2008) also supports this, noting that residents often feel "invisible" in mainstream disaster management, receiving a "standard package" of assistance that fails to account for their specific medical, nutritional, and psychological needs.

Regarding the first objective, the theme of Knowledge, Awareness, and Risk Communication reveals that older adults often experience a significant "digital information gap"; and this was also mentioned in the study by Marchand (2022) that 61% of individuals aged 75 and above have never used the internet, leading to a heavy reliance on television or word-of-mouth for alerts. This lack of direct access to digital platforms often leads to spatial optimism bias underestimating the risk involved in hazardous events like cyclones, in which residents believe their specific institutional location is immune to hazards, based on limited or misunderstood information, lacking a basic understanding of support mechanisms existing for elderly in disaster risk reduction which excludes them from disaster management practices especially in institutionalized setting. Bodstein et al., (2014) study also backs the result through an intersectional lens, age-related sensory decline, such as vision and hearing loss, intersects with institutional isolation, making it difficult for residents to interpret or act upon emergency announcements correctly. These findings highlight a disconnect with National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) guidelines, which advocate for multi-lingual, customised alerts delivered via diverse channels, yet these systems are often beyond the "fluid abilities" of the cognitively impaired elderly to navigate effectively (Marchand, 2022).

In exploring the second objective, the themes of Lived Experiences and Institutional Care highlight a high prevalence of relocation trauma, where the stress of being moved to an unfamiliar environment and the lack of freedom in the institutionalised setting are perceived as more dangerous than the hazard itself. Lived experiences are frequently marked by a sense of being "left behind" or abandoned by caregivers, a phenomenon documented in global literature where 75% of those who died during Hurricane Katrina and 56% in the 2011 Japanese Tsunami were older adults (Hutton, 2008). The study findings suggest that institutionalised elderly often feel they have "no value", and they have no faith, as responses historically treat them as passive recipients rather than active participants (Malak et al., 2025). This is compounded by a strong "attachment to place", which often drives a desire to return prematurely to their rooms or homes, viewing the loss of routine and personal space as a greater threat than the physical storm (Marchand, 2022). The respondents' risk perception of cyclones is profoundly shaped by a confluence of prior lived experiences, media sources such as television and radio news, and interactions with prior social support groups, aligning closely with established findings in literature on elderly populations.

Analysis of the third objective through the theme of Institutional Care, Collective Support, and Safety reveals a stark discrepancy between NDMA cyclone management guidelines and actual institutional conditions, as noted by the National Disaster Management Authority and Vij (2008). While NDMA guidelines specify that multi-purpose shelters should feature ramps, non-slip floors, and separate sanitation for women, Hota and Rishi (2017) reported that residents experienced overcrowding, unhygienic facilities, and a total lack of wheelchairs or handrails. These structural failings violate active ageing principles, particularly the pillar of "Security," which Edwards (2002) emphasises as the right to protection and dignity during crises. The report *Challenges Related to Ageing Population* (2025) argues that a "one-size-fits-all" approach to institutional planning fails to address the 33% of elderly who require walkers or those dependent on electricity for medical equipment, rendering current structural measures inadequate for the "ageing of the aged." During cyclones, when downstairs areas flood, elderly respondents in institutions struggle significantly to climb stairs to reach safer places upstairs, highlighting profound accessibility barriers in these facilities. This physical challenge, exacerbated by age-related mobility limitations like difficulty navigating steps during cyclonic events, contrasts sharply with community settings,

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where participants could more readily shift to safer spots upon alerts, and aligns with broader research on institutionalised elderly facing heightened vulnerability due to non-adapted infrastructure.

Finally, the fourth objective, identifying fears and coping strategies, is understood through the themes of Emotional Responses, Coping Mechanisms, and Perceived Needs. Faith and spiritual surrender emerge as primary coping strategies, with many residents surrendering themselves to god, and they believe in god more than institutional, government mechanisms, which also shows the exclusiveness in planning disaster risk reduction in the institution, as they are more oriented towards a belief system rather than practical solutions. Post-cyclone PTSD, depression, and agitation are prevalent, yet Marchand (2022) identified a critical need for Psychological First Aid and positive mental stimulation to maintain well-being during extended shelter-in-place events. From an intersectional perspective, the report *Challenges Related to Ageing Population (2025)* highlights that elderly women face a unique "emotional rollercoaster" as they often assume heavy caregiving burdens for grandchildren while simultaneously managing their own declining health and economic vulnerability. To build resilience, Hutton (2008) and Marchand (2022) emphasised residents' urgent need for senior registries and mobile medical teams to ensure medication continuity during extended power outages. This study reveals yoga as a vital coping strategy for institutionalised elderly post-cyclone, with respondents reporting reduced stress levels during heightened anxiety, as one respondent expressed as "During stress time yoga helps us." Active ageing further emerges as a key resilience factor, where stronger elderly support frailer peers by draining floodwater or providing assistance to drain down waterlogging and volunteering in evacuation, recovery, and rehabilitation, exemplified by one respondent: "If one or two persons are strong in our institution, they provide support to all others."

These findings underscore the role of active ageing in fostering inclusivity within institutional disaster management policy, transforming vulnerable elderly people into active contributors rather than passive recipients, despite their rare involvement in preparedness planning and elderly-based disaster risk reduction. This aligns with global evidence from WHO frameworks, showing that physically capable older adults (60+) strengthen peer networks, reducing isolation and boosting collective efficacy during crises such as coastal cyclones in India.

This study's strength lies in its qualitative FGD approach, which captured rich, context-specific experiences of institutionalised elderly women in a cyclone-prone region of the Union Territory of Puducherry. The use of intersectionality theory enhanced understanding of how age, gender, health, and institutional living shape risk perception among the elderly population. However, findings are limited by the single-institution setting, small sample size, and reliance on self-reported experiences, but these study findings will enhance the understanding of disaster risk perception in institutionalised settings that focus on a specific population and how this population can be integrated into the planning of disaster risk reduction. The focus on institutionalised elderly women also limits insights into the experiences of elderly men and community-dwelling older adults, but the lack of family support for the elderly women is captured in the study.

The findings emphasise the need for age-responsive and age-transformative disaster preparedness for institutionalised elderly populations with inclusive participation from the elderly population. Risk communication should extend beyond digital platforms to include sensory-friendly and face-to-face alerts based on advanced technology like AI that account for cognitive and sensory limitations. Old-age homes in cyclone-prone regions should develop institution-specific preparedness plans, including clear evacuation protocols, the need for structural changes to buildings to make them accessible for vulnerable populations during hazardous events, and role allocation. Rules and regulations, including guidelines, should be strengthened by the government, as accessibility of buildings, improper drainage were reported by participants in the study. Strengthening medical continuity, accessible infrastructure, and trained caregivers within institutions is essential. Social work intervention can be utilised to mobilise the elderly population in disaster risk reduction planning to make it more inclusive, as social workers are experts in promoting active ageing. Integrating active ageing principles by involving elderly residents in preparedness activities can enhance dignity, participation, and resilience rather than reinforcing dependency.

At the policy level, NDMA guidelines should explicitly incorporate provisions for institutionalised elderly populations rather than broader guidelines for the elderly population. Beyond basic relief such as food and shelter, disaster preparedness policies should promote elderly participation through structured activities, such as yoga-based stress management, volunteer roles, and mock drills. Although such participatory approaches remain underdeveloped in Indian institutional settings, evidence from community resilience initiatives in Puducherry suggests that elder-led preparedness and drills can improve long-term cyclone readiness. Institutionalising these practices through policy can shift disaster management from a care-centric to an empowerment-oriented approach.

CONCLUSION

This research examined cyclone risk perception among institutionalised elderly women in Puducherry, a cyclone-prone region, highlighting how risk is shaped by lived experiences, physical vulnerability, coping strategies employed, and dependence on institutional care. Findings show that while institutional settings provide critical safety and continuity of care during cyclones, residents have limited awareness of formal disaster management practices, and they have low expectations from external support, showing a gap in inclusive planning for disaster risk reduction, which needs to be addressed through active engagement of the elderly population. Fragile family ties and reliance on faith further influence acceptance and resignation toward disaster risks. The

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study underscores the need for age-inclusive and age-transformative disaster preparedness that strengthens risk communication, institutional readiness, psychosocial support, and elderly participation to ensure dignified and inclusive disaster responses in cyclone-prone regions.

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Data Availability Statement: The qualitative data generated during this study are not publicly available due to ethical considerations and confidentiality agreements with participants, but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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